

growth medium (Table 1). SG36 showed marked growth reduction.

XZN 1 absorbed more Cu, Mn, Fe, K, Na, Mg, and Ca from the K-deficient growth medium (Table 2). SG36 increased absorption of only Zn, Mg, Na, and Ca. Fe and K absorption by XZN 1 was higher than that by SG36, but SG36 absorbed more Zn and Na.

It appears that in XZN 1, Fe, Mn, Mg, Na, and Ca substituted for K. These clear varietal differences in adaptability to low K availability indicates that breeding for K-deficient soils should be possible. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Table 1. Dry weight of seedlings grown in complete and K-deficient nutrient solutions

Days after sowing	Dry weight (mg/plant)			
	XZN 1		SG36	
	Complete	Deficient	Complete	Deficient
34	34.0	36.0	36.0	29.0
38	129.0	124.0	125.0	74.0
41	135.0	135.0	135.0	88.0

Table 2. Mineral content of 38-d-old shoots.

Element	Content (% dry weight)			
	XZN 1		SG36	
	Complete	Deficient	Complete	Deficient
Cu	2.0×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-3}	1.8×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-3}
Mn	9.5×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-2}	2.4×10^{-2}	1.1×10^{-2}
Zn	2.5×10^{-2}	3.1×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-2}	4.7×10^{-2}
Fe ^a	3.8×10^{-2}	4.4×10^{-2}	4.3×10^{-2}	3.6×10^{-2}
Mg	0.40	0.65	0.58	0.77
K	3.09	1.49	2.93	0.63
Na	6.3×10^{-2}	0.24	0.12	0.76
Ca ^a	0.23	0.29	0.20	0.30

^aSampled 50 d after sowing.

Integrated germplasm improvement—general

CO 45, a new, medium-duration rice variety for Tamil Nadu

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TNAU80042 (IR17492-18-10-2-2-2) is a derivative of Rathu Heenati/IR3403-

267-1. It was named CO 45 and released in Jan 1990 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu. It can be used as an alternate to IR20 and CO 43 in the second crop season (Sep-Oct).

CO 45 is 75-80 cm tall and matures in 140 d. Grain is long and slender with white rice.

It yielded an average 5.9 t/ha (10% more than CO 43) in breeding station trials 1980-81 to 1988-89. In multilocation trials 1985-86 to 1988-89, it yielded 4.1% higher than CO 43 and 14.9%

higher than IR20. In adaptive research trials in 10 districts 1987-88 to 1988-89, it yielded 10% higher than CO 43. In national trials 1985 and 1987, it yielded 17% more than Jaya and Pankaj (see table).

CO 45 is resistant to green leafhopper, stem borer, blast, bacterial blight, and tungro, and moderately resistant to sheath rot (panicle exertion is better than that of sheath rot-susceptible CO 43). ■

Chandan, a multiple-resistance variety released in Andhra Pradesh

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RNR74802, a semidwarf medium-duration culture derived from Sona/Manoharsali, was released in Sep 1989 as Chandan. It is recommended for general cultivation in Andhra Pradesh.

In yield trials in 1977-87, RNR74802 averaged 5.6 t/ha. That is 35% higher

Performance of CO 45 in Tamil Nadu, India, 1980-89.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)					Increase (%)			
	CO 45	CO 43	IR20	Jaya	Pankaj	CO 43	IR20	Jaya	Pankaj
Breeding station									
Coimbatore (1980-81 to 1988-89)	5.8	5.3	-	-	-	10	-	-	-
Multilocation trials (1985-86 to 1988-89)	4.8	4.6	4.2	-	-	4	15	-	-
Adaptive research trials (1987-88)	5.8	5.6	5.4	-	-	4	7	-	-
Adaptive research trials (1988-89)	6.2	5.4	5.2	-	-	15	19	-	-
National trials (AICRIP 1985)	5.0	-	-	4.3	-	-	-	17	-
National trials (AICRIP 1987)	5.3	-	-	-	4.5	-	-	-	18

than Dhanyalaxmi, 23% higher than Prakash, and 48% higher than IR32 in the wet season and 43% higher than IR32, 22% higher than Prakash, and 14% higher than Laxmi in the dry season. In farmers' field trials, it outyielded Prakash by 38%. Tellahamsa

by 25%, and Samba-Mahsuri by 14%.

Chandan is photoperiod-sensitive, with 145-d duration in the wet season and 155 d (due to low night temperatures) in the dry season in Telangana region. It is resistant to brown planthopper and blast, and moderately resistant to bacterial

blight, sheath blight, and gall midge.

Grain is long slender, straw glumed with small awns, 3.9 L/B ratio. Kernels are white, translucent, flinty, nonglutinous with 10.7% protein content. Cooking quality is good. Up to 55-d-old seedlings can be planted without much yield loss. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — rainfed lowland

Performance of promising rainfed lowland rice cultivars in West Bengal

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In West Bengal, rainfed lowland rice faces occasional floods and prolonged waterlogging in the wet season. Medium-tall, stiff-strawed, and nonlodging cultivars should do better than traditional varieties.

We evaluated 10 promising lines during 1986 and 1987 wet seasons. The cultivars were transplanted 30 Aug 1986 and 4 Aug 1987 at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 18-m² plots, in a randomized block design. Fertilizer (60-17.6-24.9 kg NPK/ha) was basally applied at transplanting. Water depth during crop growth was 25-30 cm.

Yields and yield attributes of lowland rice varieties and cultures. West Bengal, India, 1986-87.

Cultivar	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)			Panicle wt (g)		
		1986	1987	Mean	1987	1986	1987	Mean	1986	1987	Mean
CR1030	112	5.2	6.0	5.6	8.9	249	303	276	2.8	3.4	3.1
Pankaj	119	4.4	6.1	5.1	8.6	245	305	225	2.8	2.9	2.9
Jagannath	115	3.7	5.4	4.5	7.4	232	297.5	265	2.2	3.1	2.7
IET7590	122	4.5	7.1	5.8	7.8	242	280	261	3.2	3.3	3.2
IET7044	119	4.4	5.2	4.8	6.6	231	254	242	3.2	3.8	3.5
CR1018	119	4.3	5.4	4.8	7.0	144	283	113	2.9	3.2	3.0
IET7592	122	4.0	6.1	5.6	9.0	205	273	239	2.8	4.5	3.7
CR1016	120	3.7	5.5	4.6	6.7	152	282	217	3.0	3.0	3.0
IET7598	118	4.2	5.4	4.8	6.2	232	281	256	2.6	3.5	3.1
Mahsuri	121	3.8	5.0	4.4	6.5	205	272.5	239	2.5	3.7	3.1
LSD ^a (0.05)		0.8	1.0		1.5	10	ns		0.04	ns	
cv (%)		0.8	7.6		9.3	2	12		0.7	10.6	

^aNS = not significant.

IET7590 had the highest yield (5.8 t/ha), followed by IET7592, CR1030, and Pankaj (see table). Straw yield was highest in IET7592 (9.0 t/ha),

followed by CR1030, Pankaj, and IET7590.

Panicles/m² was highest in CR1030 and panicle weight in IET7592. ■

Two promising high-quality rice breeding lines in Bangladesh

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We crossed C22 with IR9752-136-2 in 1981 at BRRI and developed BR4290-3-1-10 and BR4290-3-3-5 breeding lines.

Both lines have intermediate plant height, short duration, high yield potential, and moderate resistance to lodging and tolerance for drought.

In 3 yr trials at different locations, BR4290-3-1-10 outyielded by an average 45%, local check varieties with similar

Table 1. Some agronomic traits and yield of 2 promising breeding lines in rainfed lowlands. Bangladesh, 1987-89.

Line	Mean plant height (cm)	Mean duration (d)	Mean grain yield ^a (tha)					Mean yield (tha)
			On station		Outreach station		On farm	
			1987 (1)	1988 (5)	1988 (3)	1989 (4)		
BR4290-3-1-10	98	100	1.9	2.0	2.3	3.2	2.5	2.4
BR4290-3-3-5	103	103	2.0	1.9	1.9	2.8	2.3	2.2
BR21 (standard check)	100	103	1.6	-	2.2	2.8	2.4	2.2
Local check	105	100	1.5	1.8	0.9	2.3	1.9	1.6

^aNumbers in parentheses give number of locations.

growth duration (Table 1). BR4290-3-3-5 outyielded local check 31%, with similar growth duration.

Both lines possess higher milling outturn, L/B ratio, and protein percent-

age; intermediate amylose content; and shorter cooking time than check varieties (Table 2).

In 1989 regional farmers' yield trials, the lines showed wide adaptability. ■